

A Tiny 4Q33 (4QDeut^f) Fragment (PAM 43.221; IAA 204600)

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The photograph PAM 43.221¹ seems to be a photograph with a range of different Cave 4 Pentateuch fragments, and the plate may have been composed for this photograph only, after which the fragments were transferred to other plates. Thus, this photograph has fragments from 4Q1, 4Q5, 4Q8, 4Q14, 4Q24, 4Q29, 4Q30, 4Q31, 4Q33, and 4Q364, and a few I have not yet identified.

At the bottom right of the photograph, two fragments are placed side by side, the large left one published as 4Q33 (4QDeut^f) frag. 27, and the small one at the right not published in the DJD series.

section from PAM 43.221; photo Najib Anton Albina

A much later photograph, IAA 204600,² contains again 4Q30, and at the bottom six fragments from other Deuteronomy manuscripts. The tag at the bottom right qualifies the plate as “Dt Misc White”. The bottom row of fragments of this photograph includes the two mentioned fragments from PAM 43.221, though not anymore placed side by side.

bottom section IAA 204600; photographer unknown

¹<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284669>

²<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-298663>

While the three larger fragments to the right have been published by Sidnie White [Crawford] as 4Q33 frag. 27, 4Q34 frag. 2, and 4Q34 frag. 6; the three smaller one to the left have not been included in the DJD XIV volume.³

The fragment third from the left on IAA 204600 had been associated previously, on PAM 43.160⁴, with 4Q34, and placed to the right of 4Q34 frag. 9, where it would seem to form a fitting distant join (but the distance between the fragments should be somewhat larger).⁵

section PAM 43.160; photo Najib Anton Albina

4Q34 frags. 6-9 + 12

[שמו שם ובאת אל הכהן אשר יהיה] בימים [ההם] ואמרת אליו הגדתי	11
[היום ליהוה אלהיך כי באתי אל הארץ א]שׁר [נ]שׁבע יהוה לאבתינו לתת	12

It is not clear to me why the fragment was taken from the 4Q34 plate and transferred to the plate photographed on IAA 204600.⁶

The fragment second to the left reads מפני with another letter, and has not been published.

The most left fragment on IAA 20460 was associated on PAM 43.221 with a 4Q33 fragment. Indeed, the hand seems the same, and the remaining letters fit well in Deuteronomy. One may read [שׁכח את] and the fragment could be placed to the right of 4Q33 frag. 6, in 4Q33 frags. 4-6 line 13, reading

[פן ת]שׁכח את[יהוה] אלהיך לבלתי שמר[מצותיו]

³White Crawford, Sidnie, et al. *Qumran Cave 4, IX: Deuteronomy, Joshua, Judges, Kings*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert XIV (Oxford: Clarendon, 1995).

⁴<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284942>

⁵See also Eibert Tigchelaar, "Minuscule Qumranica I." *Revue de Qumran* 21/84 (2004), 643-48, at 646.

⁶The present number of the plate, which contains all of 4Q31, is unknown to me.